

Explaining decisions of a light weight deep network model for Coronary Artery Disease classification in Magnetic Resonance Imaging

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Abstract

In certain healthcare settings such as emergency or critical care units, where quick and accurate real-time analysis and decision-making are required, the healthcare system can leverage the power of artificial intelligence (AI) models to support decision-making and prevent complications. This paper investigates the optimization of healthcare AI models based on time complexity, hyper-parameter tuning, and XAI for a classification task. The paper highlights the significance of a light weight convolutional neural network (CNN) alone or in combination with other classifiers, e.g. CNN-RandomForest (CNN-RF) for analysing and classifying Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). The role of hyper-parameter is also examined in finding optimal configurations that enhance the model's performance while efficiently utilizing the limited computational resources. Finally, the benefits of incorporating the XAI technique (GradCAM) in providing transparency and interpretable explanations of AI model predictions, fostering trust, and error/bias detection are explored. Using the proposed model, clinicians/cardiologists can achieve accurate and reliable results while ensuring patient's safety and answering questions imposed by GDPR. The proposed investigative study will advance the understanding and acceptance of AI systems in healthcare settings.

Keywords: Healthcare Models, Time Complexity, Hyper-parameter Tuning, Explainable AI, Classification.

1 Introduction

According to the World Health Organization ¹, in 2019 an estimated 17.9 million people died from cardiovascular diseases, representing 32% of all global deaths. Statistics published by the American Heart Association in 2023 state that from 2017-2020, an estimated 20.5 million Americans had coronary heart disease (CHD) [Tsao et al., 2023]. Specifically, Coronary artery disease (CAD) accounts for approximately 610,000 deaths annually in the United States and is the third leading cause of death worldwide, with 17.8 million deaths annually [Brown et al., 2020].

The patient's symptoms of CAD are neither sensitive nor specific thus making it difficult for clinicians or cardiologists to rely only on them. The reference standard for CAD detection is through coronary angiography which is an invasive diagnostic imaging procedure done using cardiac catheterisation. This method is expensive and carries potential risks. Other methods include cardiac imaging techniques, which are safe, non-invasive, cheaper and can help doctors in early detection and provide timely interventions to treat CAD patients. These techniques include X-rays, Computer Tomography (CT), Echo-cardiogram and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) or Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (CMR) Imaging.

Among these techniques, CMR imaging uses magnetic waves and is considered a viable alternative for the non-invasive assessment of CAD. MRI/CMR images provide precise measurements of heart structure and functions, as well as myocardial perfusion and parametric quantification. Manual interpretation of these scans is time-consuming and needs expertise. Thus, artificial intelligence methods are exploited to automate the CAD diagnosis to reduce the analysis time with potentially improved accuracy.

¹<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-%28cvds%29>

1.1 Related Work

Recently, Khozeimeh *et al.* [Khozeimeh et al., 2022] adopted a hybrid approach (CNN-RF model) combining random forest (RF) and convolutional neural networks (CNN) to develop a novel classification method. They trained their model with three different optimizers (Adagrad, RMSprop and Adam) and reported the results.

The authors used 2D CMR images. Their pre-processing steps included resizing the images to 100x100 pixels and normalization between 0 and 1. The next step was feature generation using 10 CNNs, where each CNN was two-layered. The CNNs convert the input images into vectors of real value. For classification, Random Forest is fed with the feature vector generated by the CNN model. This approach preserves the inter-pixel spatial relationship and avoids the issue of dimensionality associated with pixel-by-pixel feeding.

A 5-fold cross-validation approach was implemented for training 10 CNN models. The trained CNNs were then used to generate a decision tree in the random forest, and based on the decision trees, the random forest determines whether the test image has CAD or not. For the final prediction, majority voting between decision trees was implemented. The authors also provide an open-source dataset of CAD Cardiac MRI repository² and reported to achieve a classification accuracy of 99.18% using Adam optimizer. Our objective in this work is to show that a single properly designed lightweight deep neural network can achieve better performance than an ensemble approach of multiple CNN models.

2 Proposed Work

In the proposed work, we implemented a lightweight deep convolutional neural network similar to the LeNET-5 model trained on the above-mentioned dataset for a comprehensive comparison. The motivation behind the proposed work is to propose a lightweight deep network model to reduce training and inference time and complexity while maintaining accuracy, enabling real-time or near-real-time CAD diagnosis. We optimized the deep model by exploring different hyper-parameter settings to identify configurations that maximize the model's performance. Furthermore, to understand why certain decisions are made, we used GradCam [Selvaraju et al.,] an XAI technique to provide interpretable insights into the decision-making process of the model, generating heat maps that highlight the regions of MRI / CMR images that contribute to the classification of CAD in respective categories.

Dataset description The dataset consists of 63,151 multiparametric CMR images that include 37,290 healthy images and 25,861 CAD patients. CAD diagnosis was confirmed by invasive coronary angiography. During the pre-processing stage, a manual inspection was conducted on images from both subsets, and any images with poor MRI/CMR quality were excluded from further analysis. Following the pre-processing stage, the dataset consisted of 34,216 images from healthy patients and 17,438 images from patients with CAD.

Performance Assessment Matrices The performance of the classifier is assessed using Positive Predictive Value (PPV), Recall (Sensitivity or True Positive Rate), Specificity (True Negative Rate), F1-Score, Area Under the Curve (AUC), Accuracy and Balanced Accuracy.

3 Results

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed model inspired from LeNET-5 architecture³. All the experiments were implemented in Python using Keras library⁴. The models were trained on Apple M2 Pro with 16 GB RAM. The following subsections discuss the time complexity calculations, the effect of hyper-parameter tuning, and feature explanations using XAI results.

3.1 Time Complexity Calculation and Comparison

²<https://www.kaggle.com/danialsharifrazi/cad-cardiac-mri-dataset>

³https://d2l.ai/chapter_convolutional-neural-networks/lenet.html

⁴<https://keras.io/>

The time taken by a model is determined by the number of layers and the operations performed in each layer. The proposed model comprises of seven layers as shown in figure 1, excluding the input layer. The input image shape was (100,100,1), in model 1 the number of filters in each convolutional layer i.e. C1 and C3 is 6, whereas in model 2 it is 12 in C1 and 6 in C3, the kernel size in convolutional layers is 5x5 (with stride (2,2)) and 2x2 in pooling layers, neurons in fully connected layer 1 and 2 are 128 and 84, respectively. Whereas, the output layer has only 1 unit, as the model is performing binary classification.

Figure 1: Proposed Model Architecture

Considering the previously mentioned size, our model is much smaller compared to the CNN-RF ensemble model in [Khozeimeh et al., 2022]. Our inference time on a MacBook laptop for 323 test images of size 100x100 is only 2.6 sec, which is only 8 milliseconds per image. Additionally, it provides better or equal classification accuracy. Our model’s lower computational complexity enables faster image analysis and diagnosis, improving efficiency, and facilitating deployment on resource-constrained systems.

3.2 Hyper-parameter tuning and classification results

We explored various hyperparameter configurations to achieve optimal model performance for CAD image classification. The PReLU activation function combined with the RMSprop optimizer resulted in the highest classification accuracy, achieving 99.35% overall and a 99.13% balanced accuracy. This surpasses the previously achieved highest accuracy of 99.18% obtained by the reference CNN-RF model, see table 1.

Table 1: Model performances achieved with different settings: Comparison

Model	Activation Function	Optimizer	PPV	Recall	Specificity	F1-Score	AUC	Accuracy
Our Model 1	PReLU	Adam	99.19	98.03	99.59	98.60	99.88	99.06
Our Model 2	PReLU	RMSprop	99.62	98.45	99.81	99.04	99.92	99.35
CNN-RF	ReLU	Adam	100	98.88	99.66	99.70	99.00	99.18

3.3 Explaining the decision with GradCAM

Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) [Selvaraju et al.,] is an explainable AI technique used to generate a heatmap of the important regions in an image that significantly contributes to the deep learning model’s prediction. Figure 2 illustrates some examples of generated GradCAM heatmaps highlighting the focused regions (region of interest) for the prediction of CAD in test images. In the GradCAM visualization, the intensity of the heatmap represents the importance of each pixel in the input image. Higher intensity (e.g., brighter colours) and high contrast colour with respect to the background are indicative of a more significant region that contributed to the model’s prediction. Figure 2(a) shows an image with CAD, therefore, the XAI technique highlighted the region of interest with a pattern of bluish in the centre and yellowish from sides that are predicting the image with a disease. Whereas, 2(b) is an abnormal (CAD) image but misclassified. Its heatmap is yellowish as a whole unlike the images correctly classified as having patterns of blue and yellow.

4 Conclusion

Considering that time and hyper-parameter tuning play a vital role in the development of healthcare AI models, optimizing them to be resource efficient, suitable for real-time applications, and ensuring the reliability of the

(a) Normal case - Region of interest is shown with bluish color in the center

(b) Region of interest: The bright region around the center (misclassified)

Figure 2: Heatmaps generated by GradCAM on test images

model is important. In addition, XAI provides interpretability and fosters an understanding of the model's decision-making. XAI helps in ensuring AI recommendations are aligned with clinical experts' interpretations, making them safer and GDPR compliant.

The CNN-RF (baseline) and proposed models were presented for the diagnosis of CAD patients using open-access 2D CMR images. The models perform binary classification and distinguish normal images from abnormal/sick patients' images. The classification model performance was measured using PPV, Recall, Specificity, F1-Score, AUC and Accuracy matrices. As the dataset has a small class imbalance, an additional performance metric i.e., Balance Accuracy was calculated. The combination of different hyperparameters revealed different classification accuracy, tabulated in table 1. Among all the settings, our model (model 2) achieved the highest test accuracy of 99.35% (with balanced accuracy = 99.13%) with activation function 'PReLU', RMSprop optimizer, batch size of 32 and binary-crossentropy as loss-function.

The proposed investigative work aimed to provide insights into the optimization of healthcare AI models, ensuring accurate and reliable results with a small lightweight convolutional neural network while prioritizing patient safety, and advancing the acceptance and understanding of AI in healthcare settings. While the results on the 2D CMR images are promising, in future investigated CNN-based models will be tested on other healthcare images such as Computer Tomography (CT), X-rays and/or Echocardiogram (Echos) images to determine the model's comprehensive diagnostic capabilities, cross-domain scalability, and performance on multi-model data.

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